

Stage 1: Initial Review (August 2025)

Search → Screening → Full-Text Assessment → Data Extraction → Classification

Initial Findings

Analysis → Initial Dataset (N=74)

Stage 2: Update Review (May 2026)

Search → Screening → Full-Text Assessment → Data Extraction → Classification

Merging

Dataset Integration → Classification Validation → Data Normalization

Final Findings

Analysis → Final Dataset (N=212)